

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT

(WITH AN ACCOUNT OF THE PROGRESS OF THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL.)

WILLIAM WILLETT

NINETEENTH EDITION.

MARCH, 1914.

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT

www.pettswoodvillage.co.uk

EVERYONE appreciates the long light evenings. Everyone laments their shrinkage as Autumn approaches, and nearly every~

one has given utterance to a regret that the clear bright light of early morning, during Spring and Summer months, is so seldom seen or used.

Nevertheless, Standard time remains so fixed, that for nearly half the year the sun shines for several hours each day, while we are asleep, and is rapidly nearing the horizon when we reach home after the work of the day is over. There then remains only a brief spell of declining daylight in which to spend the short period of leisure at our disposal.

NOW, if one of the hours of sunlight wasted in the morning could be added to the end of the day, many advantages would be gained by all, and especially by those who would spend in the open air, whatever time they might have at their disposal after the duties of the day have been discharged.

By a simple expedient, these advantages can be secured. If we will reduce the length of one Sunday, in the Spring, by 60 minutes, a loss of which no one would be conscious, we shall have 60 minutes more daylight after 6 o'clock, on each succeeding day, until the Autumn.

I therefore propose, that at 2 o'clock in the morning of the third Sunday in April, Standard time shall advance 60 minutes, and on the third Sunday in September, shall recede 60 minutes. We should then have one Sunday in April 23 hours long, and one Sunday in September 25 hours long. Having made up our minds to be satisfied, on one occasion, with a Sunday of 23 hours, the advantages aimed at would follow automatically ; everything would go on just as it

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT

does now, except that the later hours of the day would bring more light with them.

Those who have travelled by sea, will remember how easily they accommodated themselves to the alterations of time on board ship, how they adjusted their watches, attended to the engagements of the day in correspondence therewith, and dismissed from their minds all recollection of the alterations that had been made. If this can take place at sea, day after day, without discomfort, may not a similar operation be possible on land. twice in the year ?

It is possible. for, in order to meet the general convenience of Queensland, New South Wales. and Victoria, Standard time in the last-mentioned State in 1895 was advanced 20 minutes. In Cape Colony, Standard time, in 1892 was advanced 16 minutes, and again in 1903, a further 30 minutes. In France 9 minutes 21 seconds in March, 19 11, and in Portugal 37 minutes on the 1st January, 1912. No confusion resulted. Alterations in Standard Time have been carried out in other parts, also, of the world, without any difficulty.

How easily an alteration can be made, is demonstrated every time one crosses the Irish Channel. As Standard Time In Great Britain does not coincide with that in Ireland, travellers between the two countries, alter their watches, backwards or forwards, 25 minutes, on or after every journey, and

think nothing of it. Is it not well worth while to perform such an easy operation twice a year, in order to secure. in addition to other advantages, the daylight equivalent of a half holiday every week, from the third Sunday in April, to the third Sunday in September ? 60 minutes a day amount in a week to seven hours. which is more than the average length of time that can advantageously be spent in exercise, in the open air, on any half-holiday.

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT

Every hour so spent, makes for health and strength of body and mind. With seven hours every week of additional opportunity, the value of existing opportunities for exercise, and recreation, would be **more** than proportionately increased. The brief period of daylight, now at our disposal, between the hours of work and sleep, is frequently insufficient for most forms of outdoor recreation, but the daily addition of an hour after 6 o'clock in the evening, would multiply several times, the usefulness of that which we already have, and the benefits afforded by parks and open spaces would be doubled.

If my proposal be adopted, those who now leave off work at 5 or 6 o'clock, will take with them the light hitherto had at 4 or 5 o'clock. On Saturdays those whose half-holiday commences at 12 or 1 o'clock. will have at their disposal as much daylight, as if it now commenced at 11 or 12 o'clock, respectively. By this yearly gain of 154 hours of useful daylight, (equivalent to 17 holidays of 9 hours each), every year of life will be leavened with additional gaiety. It is futile to say that these advantages can be secured by early rising. The exceptional exercise of this virtue, usually calls forth more sarcasm than admiration, or imitation. Leisure must follow, not precede, work, and earlier business hours are quite unattainable.

A powerful attraction of the proposal is, that any trains, excepting those carrying Continental passengers. would run in accordance with existing time tables. Trains which now start at 8 o'clock, would continue to start at 8 by the clock, those at 9 0 v clock, at 9 by the clock, and so on-there would be no alteration of inland time tables. Continental train services, only, would require special time tables. **For any trouble in which this may involve them, Railway**

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT

1
Companies would not only find ample compensation, in reduced expenditure on artificial light, but as people are more ready to travel before, than after sunset, increased passenger traffic, and consequent Profit, must also accrue to them. Tramway and Omnibus Companies, also, would carry more passengers, and reap increased dividends, and all householders would find their expenditure on artificial light, reduced.

Owing to the diminished production of gas, and electric light, less coal would be consumed, and less smoke would defile the air. In every 25 years, more than one year 9 a consumption of fuel, for these purposes, would be saved. From the diminished use of artificial light, we may fairly anticipate an appreciable benefit to eyesight, with correspondingly restricted need for the services of the oculist and optician.

These considerations bring into view the National financial aspect of the scheme. Assuming the cost of artificial light averages only one-tenth of a penny per head, per hour, and that 154 available hours of day. light can be gained then at least £2,500,000 a year (the interest on One hundred millions of the National Debt) can be saved by the people of Great Britain and Ireland.

We should not pay for these advantages by shortened sleep; on the contrary, we should sleep better, for 60 minutes more daylight in our waking hours, would leave 60 minutes more darkness for our sleeping hours.

For a year or two, some inconvenience from the variation between time in England and other countries may be experienced, but, on the whole, it would be slight, for a loss of convenience in one direction would

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT

be balanced by a gain of convenience in another Merchants dealing with Eastern Nations would gain an advantage, while those dealing with Western Nations might suffer some disadvantage. Any inconvenience that might be found, would exist for less than half the year, and would disappear when other nations follow our example.

That so many as 154 hours of daylight are, to all intents and purposes, wasted every year, is a defect in our civilisation. Let Great Britain and Ireland recognise, and remedy it. Let us not hesitate to make the effort, when the cost is so trifling. Light is one of the greatest gifts of the Creator to man. While daylight surrounds us, cheerfulness reigns, anxieties press less heavily, and courage is bred for the struggle of life. Against disease, our ever-besieging enemy, light and fresh air act as guards in our defence, and when the conflict is close, supply us with most effective weapons with which to repel the: invader. Even the blind keenly realise the difference between daylight and darkness. They are cheered. by the former, but depressed by the latter.

A new Standard Time can be established only by Act of Parliament, and therefore the Daylight: Saving Bill, as set out on page 9, has been submitted to the House of Commons. I ask those who, approve of it,

1. To represent the advantages of the proposal to. their friends, and to request Members of the House of Commons, and Members of the, House of Lords, to support the Bill.
2. To recommend the subject for consideration by County Councils, City Corporations, and Town and District Councils, Trade Unions, Debating Societies. Clubs, etc.
3. To secure the passing of the following resolutions by such Councils, and Societies.

THE WASTE OF DAYLIGHT.

SUGGESTED FORMS OF RESOLUTIONS.

- (a) " That the passing of the Daylight Saving Bill .4 would conduce to the physical, mental, 44 moral, and financial welfare of the nation, 94 and that it is deserving of the support of 44 all classes of the community.

- (b) " That a copy of this Resolution be forwarded to the Prime Minister, the Home Secretary, and the Leader of the Opposition, accom- by an expression of hope that they will give facilities for this Bill, and to the Member of Parliament for the Division, 're~ questing him to support it. "

The following is the Form of Resolution, drafted and passed, by the Corporation of the City of Manchester.

'That this Corporation approve of the proposed Daylight Saving Bill, and believing that the adoption of the principles therein embodied, would be of incalculable benefit to the community generally, and especially to those engaged in commerce and industry, desire to express the hope, that His Majesty's Government may give their early attention to the measure."

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL

Reads as follows : enacted,

Be it &c.

1. From two o'clock in the morning, Greenwich Mean Time, in the case of Great Britain, and Dublin Mean Time, in the case of Ireland, of the third Sunday in April, in each year, until two o'clock in the morning, Greenwich Mean Time, in the case of Great Britain, and Dublin Mean Time, in the case of Ireland, of the third Sunday in September in each year, the local time shall be, in the case of Great Britain, one hour in advance of Greenwich Mean Time, and in the case of Ireland, one hour in advance of Dublin Mean Time, and, from two o'clock in the morning, Greenwich Mean Time, in the case of Great Britain, and Dublin Mean Time, in the case of Ireland, of the third Sunday in September in each year, until two o'clock in the morning, Greenwich Mean Time in the case of Great Britain, and Dublin Mean Time, in the case of Ireland, of the third Sunday in April, in each year, the local time shall be, in the case of Great Britain, the same as Greenwich Mean Time, and, in the case of Ireland, the same as Dublin Mean Time.

2. The time hereby established, shall be known as Summer Season Time in Great Britain, and Ireland, and whenever any expression of time occurs in any Act of Parliament, deed, or other legal instrument, the time mentioned or referred to shall, unless it is otherwise specifically stated, be held, during the interval, from the third Sunday in April, to the third Sunday in September, as above set forth, in the case of Great Britain and Ireland, to be Summer Season Time as prescribed by this Act.

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL

Greenwich

Time. 3. Greenwich Mean Time as used for the purposes of astronomy and navigation shall not be affected by this Act.

4. This Act shall apply to the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland, and may be cited as the Summer Season Time (Great Britain and Ireland) Act. 1914.

The Bill was first introduced into the House of Commons, by Mr. ROBERT PEARCE M.P., in, 1908, secondly by Mr. T. W. DOBSON, M.P., in 1909, when 130 Members voted in its favour, and 94 against it, the second reading being carried, by a majority of 36.

In the Present House of Commons 285 Members.. have expressed their approval of the principle of the Bill. Among them are:

Liberals.	Conservatives.
Birrell, Rt. Hon. Augustine Churchill,	Balfour, Rt. Hon. A. J.
Rt. Hon. Winston George, Rt. Hon. D.	Beresford, *Admiral Lord
Lloyd Macnamara, Rt. Hon. T. J.	Charles
Masterman, C. F. G. Norman, Sir	Cave, George, K.C.
Henry Samuel, Rt. Hon. H. L.	Chamberlain, Rt. Hon. J.
	Austen
	Smith, Rt. Hon. F. E., K.C.
Labour.	Nationalists
Abraham, Rt. Hon. W. Burt, Rt.	Devlin, Joseph
Hon. Thos. Crooks, William	Hayden, J.P.
Hardie, J. Keir Macdonald, J.	Gwynn, Stephen
Ramsay Snowden, Philip	Nugent, Sir Walter R., Bt.
	O'Connor, T. P.
	Redmond, William

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL. The following 59 Members of the House of

Lords have also expressed their goodwill towards the Bill

Lord Aberconway	Marquess of Linfithgow
Lord Airedale	The Bishop of London
Lord Ampthill	Lord Lucas
The Bishop of Bath and Wells	Lord Manners
Lord Belhaven and Stanton	The Earl of Meath
Viscount Milner	
Lord Biddulph	The Earl of Morton
Lord Brownlow	Lord Napier of Magdala
The Earl of Bessborough	Lord Newton
The Bishop of Bristol	Lord Northcliffe
The Earl of Clarendon	Lord Nunburnholme
Lord Clifford	Lord O'Hagan
Lord Crawshaw	The Earl of Onslow
The Duke of Devonshire	Lord Playfair
The Earl of Drogheda	Lord Plunket
Lord Dynevor	Lord Redesdale
Lord Ebury	Earl Roberts
The Bishop of Exeter	Lord Rotherham
The Earl of Gainsborough	Earl Russell
Lord Glenconner	The Bishop of St. Albans
Viscount Gladstone	Lord Sandys
Lord Grenfell	Lord Shaftesbury
Lord Hatherton	Lord Southwark
Lord Ilkeston	Earl Stanhope
Lord Joicey	Lord Sudeley
Lord Kenyon	Lord Swaythling
Lord Kinnaird	The Bishop of Wakefield
The Earl of Kinnoull	Lord Waleran
Lord Lamington	Lord Wenlock
The Earl of Leicester	The Bishop of Worcester

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL

STATEMENT of PROGRESS to MARCH, 1914.

The first Daylight Saving Bill, introduced in the House of Commons, in 1908, was referred to a Select Committee, which examined 41 witnesses, and reported that the effect of the Bill would be (inter alia)

To facilitate the training of the Territorial Forces ;

To benefit the physique, general health, and welfare of all classes of the community ;

To reduce the industrial, commercial, and domestic expenditure, on artificial light

That the object of the Bill is desirable, and would benefit the community, if it can be generally attained, and that the weight of the evidence submitted to the Committee agrees with, and supports this view ;

That the objects proposed cannot be attained without legislation ; and

That a single alteration of the clock, one hour in April, and a similar alteration of one hour in September, is the best mode of attaining the object of the Bill.

In 1909, when the second reading was carried by 130 to 94, another Select Committee was appointed to hear further evidence.

This Committee examined 24 witnesses, and the Chairman drafted a report in favour of the Bill, but it was rejected by a majority of one. The Committee then recommended, that the Bill be not further proceeded with, owing to " great diversity of opinion," and to "doubts which have been expressed as to whether the objects of the measure can be attained by legislation without giving rise, in cases involving important interests, to serious inconvenience."

The Chairman, and Vice-Chairman, of each Committee voted in its favour.

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL.

A manifesto, set out on pages 26 and 27, protesting against this report, was, thereupon, signed by, (among others) :-

4 judges.

60 Members of Parliament.

8 Privy Councillors.

33 Lord Mayors, Lord Provosts. Mayors and Provosts.

5 Railway Chairmen and General Managers, and 10 1 other leading men.

The only opposition, of any importance, came from

(a) The Great Eastern, and the South Eastern and Chatham, Railway Companies.

(b) Some agriculturists.

(c) Some members of the theatrical profession.

(d) The Committees of the London Stock Exchange, and Liverpool Cotton Exchange.

As to (a). The opposition of the Great Eastern and South Eastern and Chatham Companies, was limited to their Continental traffic, a matter of relatively small importance, having regard to the fact, that out of a total of 1,326 million passengers carried in a year, only 1.1 millions are Continental passengers, and of

2

these, some are carried by the London, Brighton and South Coast Railway, and the London and South Western Railway. both of which Companies support the Bill. When a Bill is supported as this is, by such Railway Companies as the London and North Western. Midland, London and South Western. London, Brighton and South Coast, Great Central. Furness, and Caledonian it is clear that very little weight can be attached to any objection to it from a Railway point of view. The

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL

General Manager of the London & South-Western Railway Company estimated, that the saving in the cost of artificial light, to all the Railways in Great Britain, not including Ireland, would amount to £92,000 a year, and the General Manager of the Great Central Railway said that the number of accidents would be reduced, because 73 per cent. take place during the dark months, against 27 per cent. during the light months of the year.

As to (b). Some agriculturists gave evidence in favour of the Bill. Sir Richard Winfrey, M.P., himself a farmer, said that there would be no substantial disadvantage to agriculturists, and that there would be distinct advantages to allotment, and small holders. Mr. W. Berry, J.P., Vice-Chairman of the Kent Education Committee, one of the largest fruit growers in Kent, stated that--the extra hour of daylight in the evening would, in some seasons, enable many tons of fruit, and hops, to be picked, which would, otherwise, never be gathered at all.--

At a meeting in 1912, of the Lincolnshire Farmers Union, the Secretary said: "In piece work, and in harvest time, the Bill will not make much difference to us, " and a farmer said: "The Bill is meant for those poor devils who are grinding out their lives behind a counter, so that they can get out earlier in the evening. I have served nine years behind a counter, and know what it means. It will not affect us."

Fifty leading Fruit Merchants of Covent Garden, signed a memorial stating that the proposed change would be of the greatest benefit to the fruit trade generally.

Three Secretaries of Chambers of Agriculture wrote to me in favour of the Bill, one of them as follows:

"The passing of this Bill, will be of the greatest benefit, to every individual in the British Isles."

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL.

As to (c). Possibly fewer people would attend indoor entertainments on fine evenings in the summer months. Mr. Hayden Coffin, the well known actor, gave evidence in favour of the Bill, and Mr. C. Armbruster, Musical Adviser to the London County Council said:--" I am satisfied that the attendance of the public, to hear our bands, would be almost doubled. Thus more value would be obtained for the money spent, and while people are enjoying fresh air, and listening to music, they are kept from public houses and similar places."

The Metropolitan Public Gardens Association considers it would greatly increase the opportunities for enjoyment of Parks, and other open spaces, all over the Kingdom.

As to (d). The Stock Exchange difficulty could be overcome by Stockbrokers, and Cottonbrokers, transacting American business, working until 5 o'clock instead of 4 o'clock, until America makes an alteration in her Standard Time, parallel to that proposed here, when the difficulty would disappear. The Chambers of Commerce of London. Liverpool. Manchester, Dublin. Belfast. Cardiff, and 72 others, support the Bill (*See page 52*).

The Secretary of the Post Office stated, that only about one half of the Continental mails (representing 6 per cent. of the total handled by the Post Office). might be prejudicially affected, and that the remainder- 94 per cent. could be dealt with without difficulty. The present Postmaster General voted in favour of the Bill, and Sir Alexander F. King, K.C.B., the present Secretary of the Post Office, supports it.

Resolutions in favour of the Bill have been passed by

4 County Councils.

685 City Corporations, and Town, and District Councils, as set out on pages 29 to 51.

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL.

The Convention of Royal Burghs of Scotland (representing 199 towns).
The Conference of Urban District Councils of England and Wales. when
over 200 Councils were represented.

82 Chambers of Commerce (as set out on page 52). The Associated
Chambers of Commerce, in 1909'. 19 10, 19 11, 1912 and 1913,
The Chambers of Commerce of the British Empire: at their Congress in
June, 1912.
59 Trade Unions, and 47 branches of the Shop, Assistants' Union, and
by
Over 400 business, political and other Associations and Societies.

These resolutions supply conclusive proof, that the. business world
approves the report of the Select Committee of the House of Commons of
1908, and attaches no importance to the doubts and fears of the majority of
the Committee of 1909.

Public Meetings, presided over by the Lord Mayor,. have been held at the
Guildhall, London, in 1909, 1911 and 1912, at each of which about 1,800
persons were present, and Resolutions were passed approving the Bill, and
requesting the Government to grant facilities for its consideration by the
House of Commons.

Similar Bills have been introduced into the Parliaments of Canada, New
Zealand, Victoria (Australia), New South Wales, and Newfoundland.

The Canadian Bill was referred to a Select Committee, which, after taking
evidence, reported favourably thereon. The New Zealand Bill has been con-
sidered by a Select Committee, which also reported in its favour and it
passed a second reading, in the House of Representatives, in August,
1913.

THE DAYLIGHT SAVING BILL.

The Select Committee appointed by the Parliament of Victoria, after
examining 62 witnesses, retorted in favour of the Bill, and recommended its
adoption throughout the Commonwealth, adding that "if the " other
(Australian) States should not agree to adopt " the Bill, the advantages
arising from its adoption '(in this state (Victoria), would so greatly outweigh
any disadvantages that it should be passed into law in this State (Victoria),
as they were convinced that it would give their industrial population such an
advantage, that the other` States would necessarily have to fall into line.---

The Prime Minister of Victoria in 1913 expressed in Parliament his approval
of the Bill, and stated that he would bring the subject before the next
Conference~ of State Premiers with a view to concerted action by all the
States of the Commonwealth.

In New South Wales a Parliamentary Select Committee has been
appointed, and has commenced to hear evidence.

In the Cities of Fort William, and Port Arthur, Ontario, the principle of the Bill
has been in operation for the past three years, and in the City of Moose
Jaw, Saskatchewan, for one year. All objections have been forgotten, and
everyone is agreed upon the great benefit gained during the summer
months.

In France, the Editor of " La Petite Republique, writing on the subject said:-"
Remember how last year we advanced our clocks nine minutes & No one
complained of it. Consider the advantages to be derived from Mr. Willett's
system. Five months out of the twelve, we shall gain one hour's sunlight
each day, seven hours sunlight each week, the equivalent of what we allow
ourselves for outdoor recreation on Sunday. And note well, that we shall not
have stolen anything from the hours allotted